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students have encountered during the task.

Having been procedure utterly completed, results were explained and discussed. According to the experiment, form-filling did not significantly impact the listening ability of participants. However, the labeling task had a significant effect on listening ability. The experimental group outperformed the control group, suggesting labeling enhances listening ability more effectively than form-filling. The control group showed no significant difference in pre-test and post-test results, in other words form-filling could not help you to boost their listening ability as labeling as can. This supports the conclusion that task-based language teaching methods are effective in improving listening skills.

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DESCRIPTION AND CLASSIFICATION OF LINGUISTIC MEANS EXPRESSING MODALITY

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to highlighting the linguistic means of the modality category in the Uzbek language. In it, methods of expression of modality at the lexical, morphological, phonetic and syntactic levels are thoroughly analyzed. Special attention is paid to the semantic and pragmatic features of language units representing modality. In particular, the role of tools such as modal words, exclamations, forms of reference, verb moods, affixes and prepositions, tone, accent, and intonation in expressing the meaning of modality is revealed with the help of examples.

Key words: Modality, lexical means, morphological means, phonetic means, syntactic means, modal words, exclamations, verb moods, affixes and prepositions, tone, stress, intonation, communicative situation, text, pragmatics.

MODALLIKNI IFODALOVCHI LINGVISTIK VOSITALARNING TAVSIFI VA TASNIFI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola modallik kategoriyasining o'zbek tilidagi lisoniy vositalarini yoritishga bag'ishlangan. Unda modallikning leksik, morfologik, fonetik va sintaktik sathlardagi ifodalanish usullari atroflicha tahlil qilingan. Modallikni ifodalovchi til birliklarining semantik va pragmatik xususiyatlariga ham alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Xususan, modal so'zlar, undovlar, murojaat shakllari, fe'l mayllari, affiks va yuklamalar, ohang, urg'u, intonatsiya kabi vositalarning modallik ma'nolarini ifodalashdagi o'rni misollar yordamida ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Modallik, leksik vositalar, morfologik vositalar, fonetik vositalar, sintaktik vositalar, modal so'zlar, undovlar, fe'l mayllari, affiks va yuklamalar, ohang, urg'u, intonatsiya, kommunikativ vaziyat, matn, pragmatika.

ОПИСАНИЕ И КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ЯЗЫКОВЫХ СРЕДСТВ, ВЫРАЖАЮЩИХ МОДАЛЬНОСТЬ

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена освещению лингвистических средств категории модальности в узбекском языке. В ней подробно анализируются способы выражения модальности на лексическом, морфологическом, фонетическом и синтаксическом уровнях. Особое внимание уделяется семантическим и прагматическим особенностям языковых единиц, представляющих модальность. В частности, с помощью примеров раскрывается роль таких средств, как модальные слова, восклицания, формы обращения, наклонения глаголов, аффиксы и предлоги, тон, ударение и интонация в выражении значения модальности.

Ключевые слова: Модальность, лексические средства, морфологические средства, фонетические средства, синтаксические средства, модальные слова, восклицания, наклонения глаголов, аффиксы и предлоги, тон, ударение, интонация, коммуникативная ситуация, текст, прагматика.

Introduction.

To fully comprehend the essence of modality, it is necessary to comprehensively study expression means at various language levels. It is an important linguistic category that reflects the relationship of the thought expressed in a sentence to reality, as well as the speaker's subjective position towards the idea. The vocabulary, grammatical structure, and even prosodic means of language serve to manifest various forms of modality.

Literature review .

When analyzing various perspectives in world linguistics regarding the general definition and classification of the concept of modality, it is possible to observe a certain commonality among approaches. In particular, most scholars recognize it as a grammatical category closely linked with the propositional content expressed in a sentence.

As J. Lyons emphasized, this phenomenon serves to express the speaker's

personal attitude towards the propositional content reflected in the sentence. In other words, while the sentence content describes objective reality, the subjective position towards it is manifested precisely through modality. The scholar notes that modality is a category that occupies a certain place in the grammatical system of language. Its meanings are often realized through special grammatical means, including modal verbs, particles, and intonation elements [8: 790].

V. Frouliu's views on linguistic means of expressing modality reveal the multifaceted and complex nature of this phenomenon. As he emphasizes, modal meanings are transmitted through means from various language levels – grammatical, lexical, and prosodic units [3: 384].

Among grammatical means, modal verbs and modal words occupy a special place. They are considered one of the most widespread and systematic methods of expressing modality. Through modal verbs (such as “necessary”, “possible”, “obligatory”) and other grammatical forms, various modal meanings, including necessity, possibility, and obligation, are clearly and distinctly reflected.

Research methodology.

In studying the phenomenon of modality, primarily descriptive-analytical, comparative-typological, and semantic-pragmatic analysis methods have been used. Modality has been investigated within the scope of lexical, morphological, phonetic, and syntactic layers. Considering linguistic-pragmatic and contextual factors, its means of expression have been studied comprehensively. As a result of the research, a classification table of modality means has been developed.

Result and discussion.

Modality manifests itself at various levels of language, including lexical, morphological, phonetic, and syntactic layers.

I. Lexical means of expressing modality include the following:

1. Modal words: Modal words serve to express the speaker's attitude towards the thought expressed in the sentence, that is, the degree of certainty or uncertainty of the thought and the speaker's evaluation. We can observe their distinctive main features in the following:

Firstly, modal words reflect how precise or imprecise the thought expressed in the sentence is for the speaker and the speaker's subjective attitude towards this thought. They help express various cognitive-emotional states of the speaker such as confidence, doubt, assumption, and regret.

Secondly, modal words do not directly enter into grammatical relationships with sentence parts syntactically and do not perform the function of a sentence part. They are usually related to the entire sentence, adding an additional modal meaning to the overall content of the sentence.

Thirdly, modal words are morphologically invariable, meaning that no affixes are added to them and they do not form combinations with grammatical form-creating means. Modal words are considered a holistic lexical unit, and their meaning is clarified through context.

2. Interjections: Interjections primarily express the speaker's emotions and emotional attitudes, while also bringing out various modal meanings. Through

interjections, modal meanings such as surprise, amazement, wonder, joy, and delight are expressed, ensuring the expressiveness and liveliness of our speech.

For example, in the sentence “Voy, may your mother be ashamed, my son, you are guests, will they even take money for bread? Put it in your pocket, here, take it, my dear,” – the interjection “voy” expresses the speaker’s feelings of surprise and pleasure. The use of interjections bestows emotionality and expressiveness to speech. For instance: “Obbo, I said, the cursed ones are still alive, they are advising me to go out and straighten things up,” I thought. (Said Ahmad, Ufq) In this sentence, the interjection “obbo” serves to express the speaker’s inner experiences and feelings. Through the interjection “obbo”, one can sense the speaker’s amazement and surprise. Moreover, some interjections can also express doubt and hesitation. For example, in the sentence “Hm, I see his goodness” (Said Ahmad, Ufq), the interjection “hm” reflects the speaker’s doubt.

3. Address units: Through address units, the speaker’s attitude towards the listener, degree of respect, and national-cultural characteristics are reflected. According to D. Boymatova’s research, address units such as “boss”, “father”, “madam”, “sir” and address forms like “that person”, “they” are of particular importance in expressing axiological modality. For example: A woman’s voice: “Father, come in, it’s getting late.” Akbarali did not respond. (Said Ahmad, Ufq)

Address units like “boss”, “father”, “madam”, “sir” are directly addressed to a person, embodying meanings of respect, reverence, and intimacy. For instance, through the word “boss”, the speaker’s respect for the listener and acknowledgment of their status is expressed, while the word “father” reflects feelings of closeness and affection. The words “madam” and “sir” express an even higher degree of respect and reverence.

The researcher also emphasizes that address forms like “that person” and “they” have their own ethnocultural characteristics. Through the address form “that person”, deep respect towards the listener is expressed, while the plural form “they”, when used in reference to a single person, indicates an even higher degree of respect. This reflects national mentality and culture.

Furthermore, the scholar notes that axiological modality can also manifest in complicated simple sentences. In complicated simple sentences, axiological modality emerges as a result of the speaker’s evaluative activity. Evaluation requires a critical approach to the most important aspects of an object and is closely linked with linguopragmatics [2: 51].

4. Subjectively Evaluative Lexis: Evaluative words play an important role in expressing modality and reflect the speaker’s attitude and opinion. The evaluation process is directly linked to linguopragmatics and emerges as a result of the practical use of language. Evaluative words include the following units:

a) Adjectives: Through words like good, bad, excellent, beautiful, ugly, amazing, the speaker expresses their attitude and evaluates the object; b) Adverbs: Words like great, very, extremely, excessively, less also perform an evaluative function and express the speaker’s feelings; c) Nouns: Words like beauty, ability, virtue, flaw, shortcoming also embody evaluative meaning; d) Verbs: Through

words like to like, to please, to approve, to praise, the speaker's positive or negative evaluation is expressed.

II. Morphological Means:

1. Verb Moods: Grammatical means, particularly verb moods, play an important role in expressing modal meanings. In the Uzbek language, imperative and conditional moods are considered primary means of reflecting various nuances of modality. Through these moods, modal relationships such as command-request, advice, and condition find their expression in speech.

The imperative mood is a special form of the verb through which a command is expressed clearly and definitively. For example, in the sentence “The future belongs to the youth, please, let them work, create, use opportunities and conditions” (Zarafshon. January 2024), the imperative mood expresses a decisive command.

Moreover, through the imperative mood, softer modal meanings such as request, desire, and advice can also be expressed. Tone and intonation play an important role here. For instance, in the sentence “They fought for the dream of independence, did not spare themselves, let us ask ourselves what we are doing for independence” (Xalq so‘zi. January 2024), request and suggestion meanings are reflected, while in the sentence “Read more books, your worldview will expand,” an advisory meaning is expressed.

2. Affixes and Affixoids: Affixes and affixoids play an important role in expressing modal meanings. Linguist Z. Qilichev has comprehensively illuminated this issue in his scientific research. According to him, affixes and affixoids such as -gina (-kina, -qina), -cha, -choq, -chak, -loq, -jon, -xon, -oy, -voy are actively used to express the speaker's modal attitude towards objective reality and their own speech. Through these linguistic units, the speaker expresses connotative, i.e., additional, secondary meanings such as love, endearment, intensification, and sometimes even belittlement.

Affixes and affixoids are especially important in revealing characters' descriptions in literary works, highlighting characteristics such as charm, gentleness, and pleasantness. The writer also expresses their attitude and evaluation through these means. Diminutive-endearment forms are more commonly used in dialogic speech, in characters' conversations, and their meanings are manifested depending on the overall content and tone of the speech.

For example, while the words “qizcha” and “qizaloq” are semantically close, their usage and stylistic functions differ. “Qizcha” more often carries a diminutive meaning, while “qizaloq” expresses endearment and love. For instance: The young girl studying at the 24th general education school was often attracted to plays shown on television as if by magic. (Zarafshon. February 2024) Similarly, in usages like “Dilbarhon - Dilbaroy”, “Ergashvoy - Ergashjon”, affixoids reveal the relationship between characters while harmonizing meanings of endearment and respect. For example: Odiljon Sattorov, chairman of the board of the “Compatriots” public foundation, provided detailed information about the main tasks of the council of Uzbek female citizens [7: 160].

Thus, understanding the role of affixes and affixoids in a literary work and their meanings and functions is crucial. This requires analyzing each word and form in context and correctly evaluating the writer's stylistic skill.

3. Particles: Particles (affixes) are an important morphological means in the Uzbek language, attaching to the end of words and loading them with various additional meanings. This, in turn, affects the overall meaning of the sentence.

Particles mainly express the following meanings: Particles expressing question and surprise (-mi, -chi, -a (-ya)) indicate that the speaker is expecting information or confirmation from the listener. They can also express emotions of surprise and amazement. For example: Are there relevant documents for the land plot where construction work is being carried out? (Paxtakor hayoti. January 2024)

Intensifying and emphasizing particles (-ku, -u (-yu), -da, -oq (-yoq)) emphasize a specific part of a word or sentence. Through this, the speaker emphasizes and highlights their thought. For example: Smell my pet! The weed has ripened, hasn't it? (Said Ahmad, Ufq)

III. Prosodic (Phonetic) Means: Prosodic means (tone, stress, intonation) also play an important role in expressing modal meanings. Through them, the speaker's feelings, emotional state, and attitude towards the thought are reflected. The role of prosodic means in expressing modal meanings is manifested in the following:

1. Tone: Through tone, the speaker expresses their feelings and emotional attitude. For example, emotional states such as joy, surprise, and regret are conveyed to the listener through tone. The rise or fall of sentence tone, its stretching or shortening, creates various modal meanings.

2. Stress: Stress highlights the semantically important parts of a sentence and thereby emphasizes modal meanings. Depending on stress placement, various modal meanings (such as surprise, emphasis, doubt) can be expressed in the sentence meaning.

3. Intonation: Intonation plays a crucial role in determining the modal meaning of a sentence. Through intonation, communicative sentence types (declarative, interrogative, imperative) are distinguished and their modal meanings are clarified. For example, through interrogative intonation, modal meanings such as inquiry, interest, and surprise are expressed, while through imperative intonation, meanings such as commanding, calling, and advising emerge.

Prosodic means increase the emotional-expressive coloration of speech, bestowing expressiveness and emotionality. They are expressed through punctuation marks in written speech, while in oral speech they are directly heard and conveyed to the listener.

Here's a direct translation into English with citation numbers preserved:

IV. Syntactic Means:

1. Interrogative and Imperative Sentences: Each of these sentence types creates various modal meanings according to their unique tone and communicative purpose. Let's analyze their capabilities more deeply:

Interrogative sentences primarily have two communicative aims: first, to

obtain information, and second, to receive an affirmative or negative response. However, through interrogative sentences, various modal meanings such as surprise, doubt, assumption, amazement, and interest are also expressed. For example, in the sentence “Have you observed young men in military uniforms standing in formation, marching confidently?” (Vatanparvar. January 2024), there is both a request for information and a slight sense of surprise.

In interrogative sentences, the particle *-mi*, interrogative pronouns, and intonation play important roles. The specific emotion, excitement, and attitude expressed through interrogative intonation not only forms its modal meaning but also actively involves the listener in the communicative process.

Imperative sentences are used to encourage the listener to perform a specific action. Through them, various modal meanings such as command, request, advice, and demand are understood. For example: a) “Get up from your place immediately!” – a definitive command, demanding tone; b) “Please, do not be offended by me” – request, pleading tone; c) “Think carefully before making a decision” – advice, recommendation tone; d) “Come on, let’s get to work!” – a softer expression of suggestion.

In imperative sentences, the imperative mood of the verb, as well as particles like “*qani*”, “*-chi*”, “*-a/-ya*”, and interjections, intensify the modal meaning. Intonation in a commanding tone further increases their impact.

2. Rhetorical Interrogative Sentences: Rhetorical interrogative sentences are a unique form of modality. In such sentences, although a question is formally posed, no actual response is expected. On the contrary, through the interrogative form, a specific thought is conveyed to the listener, creating an impact.

The main characteristics of rhetorical interrogative sentences are: a) They express modal meanings such as surprise, amazement, mockery, and emphasis more than a genuine question. For example, in sentences like “How can this work be completed in one day?” or “Shall I tell you once more?”, the emphasis is stronger than the question;

b) They are often used to confirm or deny a truth based on life experience or general knowledge. The sentence “After all, isn’t the earth round?” reflects confirmation of general knowledge about the spherical nature of the earth;

c) Through rhetorical questions, the thoughts and psychological state of the lyrical hero or speaker are also revealed. They are typically characterized by emotionality, expressiveness, and impressiveness. For example, in the sentence “Why did fate turn away from me?”, a feeling of discontent and regret is reflected;

d) Rhetorical questions encourage the listener to observe, think about events, and ponder problem solutions. A rhetorical question about a general problem like “Why do some people become self-interested?” prompts the reader to reflect on this negative characteristic.

Rhetorical interrogative sentences are more commonly used in literary, journalistic, and scientific styles. They enliven the author’s speech, serve to express thoughts impressively, and help form specific feelings and attitudes in the reader or listener.

3. **Auxiliary Verbs:** Auxiliary verbs also load modal meaning into the thought expressed in the sentence. Here, the auxiliary verb conveys various characteristics of the action. For example, in the sentence “Robert described the ecological changes in the region”, the auxiliary verb “berdi” accompanying the main verb “described” serves to emphasize the real authenticity of the action. Even if the auxiliary verb “berdi” is omitted, the meaning of the sentence will not change, but its form will [6: 128].

4. **Incomplete Verbs:** The incomplete verbs “ekan” and “emish” load various modal meanings into the sentence (such as doubt, assumption, probability) and also increase the expressiveness of speech. For example: Some of those who consider themselves poorly provided for are supposedly skilled at extracting payment. (Zarafshon. January 2024) A. Hojiyev is recognized as one of the scholars who deeply studied incomplete verbs in Uzbek linguistics. In his scientific research, he comprehensively analyzed the semantic characteristics of the incomplete verbs “ekan” and “emish”. A. Hojiyev particularly emphasizes the role of these incomplete verbs in expressing modal meanings. In his opinion, these incomplete verbs increase the expressiveness of speech by expressing modal meanings such as time, purpose, reason, condition, and desire in a sentence.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, modality in the Uzbek language finds its expression within various language levels, particularly through lexical, morphological, phonetic, and syntactic means. Linguistic units such as modal words, interjections, address forms, evaluative words, verb moods, affixes and particles, tone, stress, and intonation serve to reveal various nuances of modality.

The semantic characteristics and usage of modal means are also intrinsically linked with a specific communicative situation and context. Therefore, it is important to comprehensively cover all language levels and study them as an integral system when researching modality. Such an approach provides an opportunity to fully understand the essence of modality.

Moreover, the diversity of means expressing modality and their mutual harmony testify to its multifaceted nature. The interconnectedness of units from various levels in expressing modal semes demonstrates the richness and perfection of our language.

It is necessary to recognize the modality category as an entity occupying a special place in the linguistic system and playing a crucial role in forming speech communication. Modal means serve to realize the speaker’s communicative purpose and convey thoughts and feelings to the listener. After all, in any communication process, the relationship between speaker and listener is reflected through modality.

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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INDUCTIVE TEACHING TECHNIQUE IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' ENGLISH GRAMMATICAL SKILL

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Abstract: This article discusses on of inductive teaching technique in improving students' English grammatical skill. The main goal of this article is to examine the effectiveness of inductive teaching techniques compare to deductive technique. A quasi-experiment on pretest-posttest-control-group design was employed to answer the research hypotheses.

Keywords: Inductive technique, grammatical ability, teaching grammar, deductive technique, research hypothesis, effectiveness of inductive teachnique, quasi-experiment.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИНДУКТИВНОЙ МЕТОДИКИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ СТУДЕНТОВ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается применение индуктивной методики обучения для улучшения грамматических навыков студентов английского языка. Основная цель этой статьи - изучить эффективность индуктивных методов обучения по сравнению с дедуктивным методом обучения. Для подтверждения гипотез исследования был